

Effect of rice stubble on stem borer hibernation

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Stem borers (SB) (*Scirpophaga* and *Sesamia* spp.) are serious rice pests in Pakistan. They hibernate in the stubble of harvested fields. The Agriculture Department recommends that stubble be destroyed soon after harvest. However, most farmers either don't till fields to destroy stubble, or else plant another crop such as wheat or shaftal (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) without thorough cultivation. Therefore, enough stubble remains for SB hibernation.

We assessed the level of SB hibernation in stubble from uncultivated fallow, cultivated fallow, and shaftal- and wheat-

Hibernation of stem borers in rice stubble in 4 fields in Muridkey and Narang, Pakistan.^a

Field	Larvae (no.)					Stubble infestation (%)	Moth emergence (%)
	Alive	Dead	Av/stubble	<i>Scirpophaga</i> sp.	<i>Sesamia</i> sp.		
<i>Muridkey</i>							
Shaftal sown	76.3	3.8	3.2	76.0	0.5	87.0	76.0
Wheat sown	22.3	16.2	1.5	21.0	1.3	39.7	52.1
Plowed fallow	16.0	24.1	1.6	15.5	0.5	24.7	30.5
Unplowed fallow	102.0	1.2	4.1	100.1	1.1	92.0	83.2
<i>Narang</i>							
Shaftal sown	121.2	3.8	4.9	120.4	0.8	93.5	78.2
Wheat sown	34.5	17.1	1.7	33.4	0.9	40.2	47.7
Plowed fallow	17.8	27.4	1.8	17.0	0.8	24.0	22.0
Unplowed fallow	146.4	4.0	6.1	140.1	1.3	98.0	87.0

^aAv of 2 years data.

sown fields. One hundred stubble were collected from each of 5-7 sites at Muridkey and Narang in Dec-Jan 1981-82 and 1982-83. A subsample of 25 stubble from each collection was dissected. Number of live and dead larvae, larval species, larvae per stubble, and percent infestation were recorded. Another subsample of 25

stubble was placed in dark cages with moisture and temperature similar to those in fields. Killing bottles were attached to an exit-to-light where the emerging moths were trapped and counted (see table).

The studies indicate that destroying rice stubble after harvest is essential to minimizing SB incidence. □

Effect of azolla on insect predators

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Azolla floats on paddy water and creates in the rice field ecosystem an additional niche that influences insect predators living on or in the water. Net samples including applied and naturally occurring azolla, paddy water, and bottom mud were taken 12 times from Oct to Dec 1982 from transplanted rice fields on the IRRI experimental farm. More predators were counted in samples taken from fields with applied azolla (303) than from other fields (191) (see table).

The water-surface inhabiting species most favored by azolla were rice hopper predators *Microvelia douglasi atrolineata*

Effect of azolla on rice insect predator populations in a rice field, IRRI farm, 6 Oct to 16 Dec 1982.

	Predators (no./family) ^a																	Total		
	Hemiptera								Coleoptera				Odonata		Araneae					
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q		R	S
With azolla	57	38	28	26	4	2	2	1	24	18	14	11	8	6	170	42	2	1	2	303
Without azolla	31	20	16	10	3	2	13.2	18	20	9	10	4	6	2.7	16	1	0	1	191	

^aTotal of 12 net samples. A = Veliidae, B = Pleidae, C = Notonectidae, D = Mesoveliidae, E = Ochtereidae, F = Nepidae, G = Gerridae, H = Belostomatidae, I = Dytiscidae, J = Hydrophilidae, K = Hydracarinae, L = Gyrinidae, M = Carabidae, N = Staphylinidae, O = Coenagrionidae, P = Libellulidae, Q = Lycosidae, R = Theridiosomatidae, S = Theridiidae, and T = Tetragnathidae.

(Bergroth) [Veliidae], *Paraplea sobrina* (Stål) [Pleidae], and *Lycosa pseudoannulata* (Boes. et Str.) [Lycosidae]. The rice bund-inhabiting spiders *Pardosa birmanica* Simon, *Arctosa janetscheki* Buchar, and *Hippasa rimandoi* Baxion [Lycosidae] moved into the azolla. Among the subsurface species, azolla favored noto-

nectid backswimmers, pleid water bugs, water treaders, and coenagrionid damselfly naiads.

Surface-dwelling gerrid water striders and the libellulid dragonfly preferred open water. Other groups of insect predators either were unaffected by azolla or were too few to allow comparisons. □

Pathogens and nematodes for control of rice water weevil in Cuba

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Rice water weevil *Lissorhoptrus brevisos-tris* (Suffr.) has few natural enemies in Cuba. We conducted laboratory and field

studies to identify fungi, bacteria, and nematodes with potential to control rice water weevil.

Various strains of *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarrhizium anisopliae* fungi were tested in the laboratory. Because rice water weevils live below the water surface, fungi cannot be applied directly to adults. Some fungi were broadcast on the water surface in the laboratory and in-

fectured insects when they surfaced. When adult rice water weevils were contaminated with *B. bassiana* strain 32, mortality was 95% at 20 days (Table 1) and 100% at 32 days after infection. When 2 kg *B. bassiana* 32 was broadcast on a 2-ha rice field adult mortality was 88% 15 days after application.

None of the *Bacillus thuringiensis* bio-preparations (Bitoxibacilin, Insectin, Den-

Table 1. Mortality of *Lissorhoptrus brevivros-tris* adults caused by *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarrhizium anisopliae* fungi, Sur del Jibaro, Sancti Spiritus, Cuba, 1978.

Fungus and strain	Rice water weevil mortality (%) 20 days after infection	
	Female	Male
	Beauveria bassiana 24	92
Beauveria bassiana 32	99	92
Metarrhizium anisopliae 12	83	79
Metarrhizium anisopliae 4	61	51

Insecticide-resistant brown planthopper populations at the IRRRI farm

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Brown planthopper (BPH) may develop resistance to some insecticides applied repeatedly. This has occurred in Japan and Taiwan, China. We found insecticide-induced BPH mortality to be much lower for populations collected from the IRRRI research farm than for greenhouse colonies (see figure).

Chlorpyrifos + BPMC has been used at IRRRI since 1978, and acephate has been used since 1981. For 10 years BPH-susceptible cultivars usually received two granular and six foliar insecticide applications per season. Using such quantities of insecticide has undoubtedly hastened the development of insecticide-resistant BPH populations at the farm. □

drobacilin, and Dipel) controlled rice water weevil when applied to 35-day-old rice plants as a foliar spray at 0.6, 1.2, and 2.4 kg/ha.

When *Neoplectana* nematodes were broadcast on the water surface in the laboratory, adult mortality was 82% between 8 and 18 days after application. In another test, three dosages of the nematode were applied. Rice water weevil damage was lowest with 36 nematodes/ml water which caused 77% adult mortality (Table 2). When the same test was

Table 2. Mortality of rice water weevil adults caused by different rates of *Neoplectana* nematode, Havana, Cuba, 1981.

Dosage (nematodes/ml water)	Rice water weevil mortality (%)
3550	80
355	82
36	17

done on rice water weevil larvae, mortality ranged from 73 to 83% 12 to 15 days after application. □

Mortality (%) 48 h after caging

Comparative mortality of greenhouse insecticide-free populations (---) and field populations (—) collected from IRRRI farm in Apr–Jun 1982 when treated with foliar sprays at 0.75 kg ai/ha.

A new gall midge parasite in M. P., India

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Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason), a destructive rice pest in India, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Vietnam, and Indonesia, has a large natural enemy complex. *Platygaster oryzae* is a dominant egg-larval gregarious parasite of gall midge. *P. oryzae* parasitism in Madhya Pradesh was 14.3% in the summer rice crop in Apr and May 1977.

During 1980 wet season a hymenopterous grub was found feeding on the pupae of *O. oryzae*. Adults were identified as *Neanastatus gracillarius* Masi (Eupelmidae: Hymenoptera) (identified by Z. Boucek). This is the first record of the parasite on *O. oryzae* in Madhya Pradesh. □

Influence of planting time on rice leaf folder incidence

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Rice leaf folder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée is a serious rice pest in samba season (Jul-Aug to Dec-Jan) at Tirur. We studied the effect of planting time on LF incidence.

IR20 was planted in 10-m² field plots on 7 dates with 4 replications during 1981–82 at PES, Tirur. Insecticide was not used. Total leaves and LF-damaged leaves on 25 randomly selected hills from

each plot were counted 60 days after transplanting and damage percentage was calculated (see table).

Leaf damage was significantly lower

Effect of planting time on rice leaf folder incidence, 1981–82 samba, Tirur, India.

Planting date	Mean leaf damage ^a (%) 60 DT
05 Aug 1981	39.7
20 Aug 1981	39.3
05 Sep 1981	41.7
20 Sep 1981	08.5
05 Oct 1981	13.2
20 Oct 1981	15.3
05 Nov 1981	13.6
CD	5.8

^aDT = days after transplanting.

(below the 20% economic threshold level) on crops planted from 20 Sep to 5 Nov. The early crop (5 Aug to 5 Sep) had heavy LF damage because maximum tillering and early flowering coincided with peak LF population (Oct–Nov).

Natural enemies of rice insect pests in Chhatisgarh (M.P.), India

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Natural enemies substantially reduce insect pest populations in rice fields. We began an intensive rapid roving monitor-